

C to Effective and Secure Rust: Are we there yet? (Extended Report)

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Abstract

RUST is a memory-safe alternative to C, fueling interest in migrating legacy codebases from C-to-RUST. This demand has led to the development of C-to-RUST transpilers. Despite their prevalence, there exists no study and dataset to systematically evaluate the effectiveness of C-to-RUST conversion techniques and the security of the generated RUST code.

In this paper, we conduct the first systematic mixed methods study to understand various aspects of C-to-RUST conversion techniques. We investigate the current state of the C-to-RUST conversion technique to study key aspects along five RQs including prevalence, conversion workflows and usability challenges. To enable systematic analysis, we created CRUSTADE dataset, a set of 61 annotated real-world C programs (across 9 categories) covering different C-language idioms. We design CRETRICS metrics, capturing syntactic, functionality, and security aspects of the converted RUST code. Our study identified various interesting findings and open-problems. For instance, our survey reveals that developers adopt an intertwined tool-assisted workflow. However, existing tools provide limited support for interactive workflows, highlighting a gap between developer needs and current tooling. We argue that our work provides a framework for evaluating conversion techniques from C-to-RUST and provides insights for future research directions.

1 Introduction

RUST [51] is a well-known secure alternative to C because it provides memory-safety guarantees while also offering performance comparable to C [86]. Given the large amount of legacy C code, there is a significant academic and federal interest in automatically converting C-to-RUST. Recently, the Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency (DARPA) released the TRACTOR program [8] with multi-million dollar funding seeking novel techniques for automated C-to-RUST conversion. There exist several tools [3, 12, 28, 40, 41, 83] enabling automated C-to-RUST conversion. But there is a lack of systematic understanding of their effectiveness, limitations, and relevance to developer needs. For example, existing evaluations are ad hoc, there is no common dataset of C programs for translation, and we lack metrics to assess the quality of generated RUST code. Furthermore, developer perspectives on the utility and challenges of these tools remain unexplored.

In this paper, we present the first mixed-methods study aimed at understanding the current landscape of C-to-RUST conversion techniques, including their limitations, developer expectations, and open problems. Our methodology combines a systematic analysis of existing C-to-RUST conversion tools with a developer survey designed to capture practitioner perspectives, workflows, challenges, and desired improvements. We uncover key limitations of current

tools through interesting findings and open problems. For instance, we observe that none of the evaluated tools adequately models C pre-processor directives, which might lead to incorrect conversions. Additionally, we also highlight semantic-equivalence checking for C-to-RUST translation as a major open problem. Developers invest considerable effort in fixing tool-produced code, not only for safety but also for type conversion. Developers need conversion tools to focus on converting C types to higher-order RUST types, which no existing tool focuses on.

We also identified a lack of a standardized, qualified C-program dataset to evaluate conversion techniques. To address this, we created the CRUSTADE dataset, a set of C programs that cover various C language idioms. *We curated and annotated a set of 61 C programs covering various C constructs and programming idioms, including real-world network servers such as inetd. We manually annotated all array pointers, i.e., both static and dynamic.* We identified that the current evaluation metrics for translating C-to-RUST are limited and do not adequately capture all aspects of the generated RUST code. For instance, the commonly preferred metric of fewer unsafe blocks does not always correspond to more secure RUST code (§ 4.2.1). *We create CRETRICS metrics, a set of 6 metrics, spanning across three categories, to comprehensively capture the syntactic, functionality, and security aspects of the generated RUST code.* We evaluated tools on C programs from the CRUSTADE¹ dataset using our CRETRICS¹ metrics. We identified shortcomings of existing tools and open problems for future translation work.

In summary, our contributions are:

- We present a systematic study of 15 C-to-RUST tools, revealing the current state of the art, key findings, and open problems.
- We conduct the first developer study on C-to-RUST conversion, uncovering practitioner expectations and challenges.
- We introduce CRUSTADE, an annotated dataset of 61 C programs (2,884 functions) covering diverse idioms and constructs (12 function types).
- We define CRETRICS, a set of 6 metrics for evaluating the syntactic, functional, stylistic, and security properties of translated RUST code.
- We evaluate 9 practical state-of-the-art C-to-RUST tools on CRUSTADE using CRETRICS, identifying key shortcomings in handling challenging C idioms and types.

2 Background on RUST

RUST [51] provides memory safety guarantees while also offering performance similar to C [86].

Low Overhead Memory Safety. RUST achieves this performance because its compiler performs safety checks primarily at compile time, adding runtime checks only when necessary. All arrays and objects are bounded, and the compiler ensures (statically or via

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runtime checks) that all accesses are within the bounds, ensuring spatial memory safety [77]. RUST achieves temporal memory safety [54] by enforcing single Ownership [11, 15] and valid lifetimes. Appendix A.2 provides more details regarding this.

unsafe Regions and Interoperability. Certain C idioms, such as raw pointers and inline assembly [13], are disallowed by default in RUST, as the compiler cannot ensure their safety. However, some programs (e.g., OS kernel) may need these idioms. RUST provides the `unsafe` keyword [16], which creates a scope permitting such idioms, though no safety guarantees apply within it. RUST has a flexible Foreign Function Interface (FFI) [64] which enabling RUST functions to interoperate with C, and tools like `bindgen` [63] and `cbindgen` [50] simplify generating the necessary bindings.

Software Organization. RUST projects use Cargo, a package manager and build tool. Cargo requires a project manifest file, `Cargo.toml` [7] (TOML-based key-value text file) in the project root. This allows RUST projects to be built using a generic command, i.e., `cargo build`. RUST also supports attributes or configurations that enable compilation specialization. These are similar to pre-processor directives and conditional compilation in C/C++, e.g., `#ifdef`.

3 State of C-to-RUST conversion

We study the current state of automated C to RUST conversion, with the aim of identifying current trends, open problems, and developer expectations. Specifically, we explore these five aspects: **RQ 1: Prevalence and Motivation** (§ 3.2): *How prevalent C-to-RUST conversion is in practice and primary motivations for conversion?*, **RQ 2: Conversion Methodology** (§ 3.3): *What methodologies are employed by existing C-to-RUST conversion tools and how these tools are used in practice?*, **RQ 3: Completeness** (§ 3.4): *How complete are the existing techniques in handling all aspects of C-based projects?*, **RQ 4: Usability** (§ 3.5): *How usable are the existing tools and what are the issues faced by developers in using them?*, and **RQ 5: Evaluation Methodology** (§ 3.6): *What is the evaluation methodology used by the existing tools and is it adequate?*

3.1 Study Methodology

We use a *selective mixed-methods approach* [69, 73], combining a developer study and systematic analysis to investigate our research questions. Specifically, we try to use a mixed-methods approach where possible; however, when it is not applicable, we use one method. For instance, we use only the developer survey to assess the prevalence of C-to-Rust conversion. However, we use both methods to understand the ease of use of conversion tools.

3.1.1 Tools Selection. We aim to perform a systematic analysis of the state-of-the-art conversion tools. We searched RUST forums and the past five years of top-tier security and software engineering conferences to identify C-to-RUST conversion tools. We only included tools that are either related to research publications, are backed by industry, or have been updated in the last 2 years. For example, we did not select CRUST [68] because it is not backed by any company and has not received any updates in the last 3 years. We also did not consider tools that are neither open-source nor publicly available, e.g., RUSTY [36].

Similarly, for LLM-based tools, we focus mainly on published ones. However, some non-published (i.e., arXiv-only) tools were

open-source and included setup instructions. We included arXiv-only tools that have source code available, and that are practical to use (i.e., can be used with reasonable manual effort), e.g., we considered C2SAFERRUST [53], but not PR2 [34], SAFETRANS[31], as the source code of these tools was not available. Furthermore, recent work by Xue *et al.* [80] shows that most existing LLM-based works fail to produce valid (i.e., compilable) RUST code. Our experiments with LLM-based tools also confirm this (as we will show in § 4.2). The selected tools are summarized in Table 1.

3.1.2 Developer Study. We performed our developer study through an anonymous online survey with 33 questions across six categories, summarized in Table 8 along with a complete list of questions (in the Appendix A.11.1). We also included attention check questions to filter out inattentive participants. Our survey was reviewed by our organization’s Institutional Review Board (IRB).

Participants Selection. We distributed the survey on various online developer forums, reddit, and mailing lists of C and Rust projects, reaching a diverse range of developers. This approach aligns with the recruitment methodology used in the recent Rust study by Sharma *et al.* [66].

Survey Respondents. We received 92 valid responses. The majority of the participants (82, 89%) identified themselves as developers. Most participants had 1-3 years of experience in both C and RUST. Nearly 40% considered themselves advanced in their RUST skills.

3.2 RQ 1: Prevalence and Motivation

We primarily use the developer survey to answer this RQ.

Prevalence Survey revealed that only 28% of the developers have performed C-to-RUST conversion. Considerable diversity in the experiences of C and RUST can be observed among developers who have converted from C to RUST. We present the details of the developers’ distribution and discuss them in Appendix A.10.1. Developers have tried to convert projects of various sizes, i.e., small (< 1K LoC) to large (> 10K LoC), including embedded system applications. Figure 9 (in Appendix) shows key characteristics of the converted C projects. Interestingly, our survey revealed that `Bindgen` [63] was the most commonly used tool. Unlike traditional C-to-RUST conversion tools, `Bindgen` is designed for interoperability rather than full translation: it operates on C header files (.h) and generates the corresponding RUST bindings, thereby allowing functions from the original C library to be invoked from RUST code. Although some developers reported using C2RUST and Large Language Models (LLMs), `Bindgen` accounted for the majority of reported usage.

This low prevalence of C to RUST conversion and the use of `Bindgen` aligns with industry practices in adopting RUST. Organizations [21, 49] mainly use RUST for new codebases, opting not to port existing ones to avoid regressions and certification costs. `Bindgen` enables the RUST code to interoperate with existing C code. Organizational factors rank low in the motivation to convert C-to-RUST, Figure 18 (in Appendix) shows a detailed distribution. Furthermore, developers in the open-source community prefer rewriting software in RUST rather than converting existing codebases [75].

These observations admit multiple interpretations. On one hand, it may raise questions about the practical relevance and necessity of existing C-to-RUST conversion efforts. On the other hand, *the low*

Table 1: Summary of C-to-RUST conversion tools evaluated as part of the study and the features that are supported.

S.No.	Tool	Goal	Conversion Methodology Sec. 3.3			Software Aspects Sec. 3.4		Validity of Conversion Sec. 3.6		Original Evaluation Sec. 3.6				Usability Sec. 3.5		
			APPR	INSt	INVE	GENB	CONF	SN	SE	Ds	NP	SzP	ME	SU	RN	INP
Static-Analysis Based Tools																
1	C2RUST [12]	Preserving semantics, Uses unsafe freely	St	✗	✗	✓	✗	✓	Tc	☰	11-20	1-10k	M	🟢	▶	🗑️
2	CROWN [83]	Reducing raw pointers	St	✗	✗	✓	✗	✓	Tc	☰	11-20	1-10k	M	🟢	▶	C2R
3	LAERTES [28]	Converting raw pointers to references and reducing unsafe	St	✗	✗	✓	✗	✓	Tc-Dv	☰	11-20	1-10k	M	🟢	▶	C2R
4	CRUSTS [3]	Reducing unsafe	St	✗	✗	✓	✗	✓	Tc	☰	≤10	1-10k	M	⚠️	▶	C2R
5	CONCRAT [40]	Replacing C lock API with Rust lock API	St	✗	✗	✓	✗	✓	Tc	☰	>20	1-10k	M	🟡	▶	C2R
6	NOPCRAT [41]	Removing output parameters in functions	St	✗	✗	✓	✗	✓	Tc	☰	>20	>10k	M	🟡	▶	C2R
LLM Based Tools																
7	Manual Combination Tools [19, 22, 81, 84, 87]	Idiomatic Rust	LM	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	⚠️	☰	>20	≤1k	M	🟢	▶	👤
8	TYMCRAT [39]	Replacing C types with idiomatic Rust types	LM	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	Tc	☰	>20	>10k	M	🟡	▶	🗑️
9	C2SAFERRUST [53]	Idiomatic Rust	LM	✗	✗	✓	✗	✓	Tc	☰	>20	>10k	M	🟡	▶	🗑️
10	EvoC2RUST [76]	Idiomatic Rust	LM	✗	✗	✓	✗	✓	Tc	☰	>20	≤1k	M	🟢	▶	C

⚠️ Only done on individual translation unit or function level.

observed prevalence may itself be a consequence of the limited maturity and usability of current conversion tools, underscoring the need for more effective tools and techniques. We presume it is the latter as developers indicated the lack of sufficient resources (e.g., documentation, examples, etc.) for C-to-RUST conversion. Figure 16 (in Appendix) indicates developers' experience with existing resources (e.g., documentation, examples, etc.) for C-to-RUST conversion.

Motivation and Perceived Benefits. Developer reported multiple motivating factors to convert C to RUST. As expected, several selected maintainability (67%) and security (38%) as the factors. Interestingly, 43% of developers also aim to learn RUST through conversion, even developers with significant prior experience in C.

Figure 10 (in Appendix) summarizes developer opinions on the benefits they expect from C-to-RUST conversion. Over 80% of developers expect the resulting RUST code to offer greater security and maintainability. Opinions on performance, however, are more divided: 66% of developers perceive no performance benefit from the converted RUST code, while others believe it may be faster – highlighting the need for systematic performance analysis, a concern also noted in recent work by Sharma et al. [66].

Finding F1: Despite ongoing efforts [8] for new C-to-RUST conversion techniques, only 28% of developers attempt the conversion.

Finding F2: The majority (>50%) of developers mention that the current resources on C-to-RUST conversion, especially documentation, are inadequate and need to be improved, e.g., with more examples.

Finding F3: Maintainability, learning RUST, and security motivate developers to convert C to RUST. Conversion tools should focus on producing both maintainable and safe RUST code.

3.3 RQ 2: Conversion Methodology

We adopt a mixed-methods approach to investigate this aspect.

Tool Approaches Here, we investigate *what* is the underlying approach used to perform the conversion, and *how* the approach is realized. The *Conversion Methodology* column group (i.e., APPR) in Table 1 summarizes our findings for each tool. The approach can be broadly classified as either static analysis (St) (e.g., AST translation [12], compiler feedback [3], points-to analysis [71], etc), dynamic analysis (DYN) (e.g., dynamic-points-to [25]), learning (LM) (e.g., LLMs), or hybrid (Hyb). The APPR column in Table 1 shows the approach used by various tools. The existing techniques can be broadly categorized into static analysis and LLM-based tools.

Static Analysis Based Tools (St). These tools used static analysis techniques (e.g., points-to analysis) to improve certain aspects of RUST code generated by C2RUST - for e.g., reducing raw pointers (LAERTES, CRUSTS), converting lock API (CONCRAT [40]), etc. Recent work by Sharma et al. [66] shows that type conversions, i.e., converting C-to-RUST types and vice versa, is one of the hard problems in C-to-RUST conversion. However, it is interesting to see less work on improving type conversion aspects.

LLM-Based Tools (LM). These techniques leverage LLMs for various aspects of conversion, utilizing prompt engineering and repair strategies to generate valid RUST code [84]. Advances in LLM reasoning allow tools to address elements overlooked by static analysis, such as type-conversion by TYMCRAT. However, the resulting RUST code often fails to compile [80], either being unbuildable on its own or containing semantic differences that disrupt the combined output. Most tools directly convert C code to RUST using LLM, while a recent technique, C2SAFERRUST, first transforms code with C2RUST and then refines it using LLM.

To tackle LLM context limits, LLM-based tools used a divide and conquer approach using three phases: (i) The original C program

is split into smaller components (*decomposition*). (ii) The components are provided to an LLM (for *translation*). (iii) The candidate translations are combined into a whole program (*composition*). In all techniques, the translation phase is mostly automated and uses various prompt engineering and repair strategies. For instance, TYMCRAT focuses on type conversion and uses prompts to convert C types to higher-level RUST types. The decomposition and composition phases differ across techniques and are dependent on the translation technique. For instance, EvoC2RUST decomposes the source C project into modules, whereas TYMCRAT and other techniques decompose into functions. Unlike the translation phases, the *decomposition and composition phases are manual* in most of the techniques. We categorized these techniques under the **Manual Composition Tools** row in Table 1. A few tools, such as TYMCRAT and EvoC2RUST, automate these phases using smart techniques, e.g., EvoC2RUST uses project templates. We categorize these tools further in Appendix A.1 and Table 4.

Developer Workflows While existing tools mainly operate in non-interactive modes, developers often use flexible and intertwined workflows in practice. Our survey indicates that *developers rarely rely solely on automated conversion and instead combine tool-based and manual steps*. Specifically, the majority (50%) first run the tool and then perform some manual fixes, while about 25% perform manual fixes before using the tool. Figure 1 shows the distribution of different types of conversion workflows for C-to-RUST conversion. The type of manual fixes varies with developer expertise. Beginners struggle with RUST’s ownership semantics, while intermediate and advanced developers encounter debugging issues. *C library and type compatibility issues affect all skill levels, highlighting a research opportunity*. Experts tackle complex C types and semantics, often relying on trial and error and refactoring rather than documentation. Figure 12 (in Appendix) shows solution strategies by RUST expertise during manual conversion.

Figure 1: Conversion Workflows adopted by developers for conversion from C to RUST.

Desired Improvements As mentioned before, developers use conversion tools in an intertwined manner. One of the necessary capabilities to enable this is interactivity [46]. In addition to incorporating manual fixes, interactivity is often necessary when there are multiple conversion choices, and developers might have preferences. For e.g., to use `String&str`, or `CString/CStr` for strings, i.e., `char *`. Unfortunately, as shown under the INVE column, none of the tools support interactivity.

Another factor that can significantly reduce manual effort is the availability of authoritative guidance on hard-to-convert C idioms, which may vary across tools. For example, one tool may handle complex data types effectively, whereas another may be better suited for handling intricate pointer manipulations. However, none of the evaluated tools provide such information about C idioms, as indicated in the INSt column. No tool investigates a translation-friendly

yet maintainable variant of C code. For example, reducing cyclic structures improves the effectiveness of alias analysis, consequently improving RUST conversion (Emre *et al.* [27]). CHECKED C might be a potential alternative with its backward compatible annotations that can be used to precisely convert array pointers to higher order RUST types, e.g., `Vec` [24].

Finding F4: Existing static analysis-based techniques use C2RUST to achieve initial conversion and then try to improve certain aspects (e.g., pointers to references, adding lifetimes, etc.) of the initial RUST code through static analysis techniques, e.g., alias analysis.

Finding F5: LLM-based tools adopt a divide-and-conquer approach by decomposing the source C project into sub-components, translating these sub-components, and then combining the resulting translations.

Finding F6: Most LLM-based tools require manual effort to decompose the original C project and combine the translated RUST code.

Finding F7: Developers claim to follow interactive conversion workflows. However, our analysis (§ 3.3) shows that none of the tools have built-in support for interactivity and indicates a research opportunity.

Finding F8: Conversion challenges differ according to developers’ expertise level. Tools can focus more on tackling certain challenges based on the expertise level of the target developers.

Open Problem P1: There exists no work on identifying conversion-friendly representations or refactorings of C code, i.e., intermediate maintainable stages. CHECKED C annotations are a potential choice, but no work has explored their use for RUST conversion.

Open Problem P2: No generalized approach exists to identify hard-to-convert C idioms, e.g., linked lists, nor is there a standard knowledge base of idioms that could enable interactivity and better conversion.

3.4 RQ 3: Completeness

In addition to converting source code, a C codebase has other software aspects that a complete conversion tool should handle. Specifically, build files and conditional compilation. We investigate the support for these aspects in the conversion tools.

Generates Build Files (GENB): As mentioned in § 2, RUST projects require `Cargo.toml` and `build.rs` (for external libraries), managed via the Cargo tool. Conversion tools should generate these files. The GENB column in Table 1 indicates whether tools generate these files, using ✓ and ✓ to indicate that the tool generates both the `Cargo.toml` and the `build.rs`, or only `Cargo.toml`, respectively.

C2RUST’s `-emit-build-files` option generates `Cargo.toml` and a placeholder `build.rs`, but *the generated build script lacks the code needed to link external libraries*. Users must manually identify and add these linking instructions. *Other static analysis-based tools, which build on C2RUST’s output, do not improve this aspect either*. Additionally, all tools fail to detect multiple targets (as specified in `Makefile` or `CMakeLists.txt`) or generate appropriate multi-target `Cargo.toml` configurations.

Handles Preprocessor Directives (CONF): Preprocessor directives, i.e., conditional compilation (e.g., `#ifdef`) and macros (e.g., `#define`, `__STDC__`), are important for C code reconfigurability, e.g., compiling for different operating systems [30]. As mentioned in § 2, RUST supports macros [61] and conditional compilation via `cfg/cfg_attr` attributes [62]. Conversion tools should translate preprocessor directives to maintain reconfigurability. The CONF column in Table 1 shows whether the tools handle preprocessor directives.

None of the tools handle preprocessor directives adequately, not even TYMCRA^T and C2SAFERRUST (LLM-based tools). While EvoC2RUST tries to handle some macros, it is inadequate. Poor macro conversion can lead to decreased maintainability, loss of functionality, and incorrect code. We provide an example in the Appendix A.7. The core challenge is that most tools operate on AST generated by clang, but preprocessor directives are resolved before AST generation, leaving tools oblivious to macros. We need techniques to identify macro-related information during preprocessing and combine it with the information at the AST parsing stage. A few works [26, 57, 70] attempt to tackle this, but integrating these ideas into a C to RUST conversion tool and validating their suitability remains unexplored.

3.5 RQ 4: Usability

We used both qualitative analysis and a developer survey to investigate the usability of the conversion tools.

Qualitative Analysis. We manually set up and run each tool and categorized the corresponding effort. The last group of columns in Table 1 summarizes our analysis.

Effort to Setup (SU): We categorize the setup effort as follows: (i) Easy (🟢): clear and straightforward commands. (ii) Medium (🟡): unspecified or deprecated dependencies needing investigation. (iii) Hard (🔴): unclear instructions requiring reverse engineering. Most tools were easy to set up using cargo build and provided instructions, except for CRUSTS, which had incorrect paths for TxL rule files, requiring extra effort to correct.

Effort to Run (RN): We check if the tool can be run in a push-button manner, using a simple command (▶), or if it requires multiple steps that the user has to update/modify (▶▶). We also check the additional inputs (INP), other than the C code, required by tools. Existing tools either require compile_commands.json file (indicated as 📄), or require the output of C2RUST tool (indicated as C2R), or just require C source files (e.g., EvoC2RUST, as indicated by C).

The situation is different with LLM-based tools, where most are **Manual Composition Tools** (§ 3.3) that require the decomposition and combination phases to be performed manually. These phases require substantial manual effort (indicated by 🧑) due to *semantic disconnect*, i.e., the same entities used across different components may be translated differently [23, 35, 88]. Consequently, combining these components requires identifying a common conversion and refactoring the rest of the RUST code. This becomes even more tedious when there are multiple types involved across multiple components. *Most of these tools also suffer from missing or incomplete documentation regarding specific requirements for running them.* We provide more details in Appendix A.5 and A.6.

Developer Survey. Few developers (14%) reported difficulties during the setup of C2RUST. Developers also faced robustness issues (e.g., crashes) in all the tools – with Bindgen being the most robust (62% reported no issues) among automated tools. This aligns with our observation (§ 3.5), where C2RUST failed to produce valid code on certain projects. Although the survey results are broadly consistent with our analysis, they should be interpreted with caution, as most developers use Bindgen (§ 3.2), and it remains unclear what challenges they may encounter when using other C-to-RUST tools.

As shown in Figure 17b (in Appendix), developers claim that most tools were easy to set up and run.

Code Quality and Manual Refactoring. Most developers were dissatisfied with the code quality generated by the conversion tools. `unsafe` usage (13% - 25%), raw pointers (12%-18%), and the lack of idiomaticity (12%-22%) remain major issues. A small percentage (9% - 12%) of developers reported that the RUST code lacked mapping with the original C code. Interestingly, developers (18%-25%) reported type safety issues with generated code; specifically, the conversion tools fail to use appropriate high-level RUST types where necessary, e.g., using `Vec` for array pointers – our analysis in § 4.2.3 confirms this. The limited codebase size support is reported as an issue with LLMs. However, with increasing context window sizes [78] and intelligent encodings [65], this issue will be less of a concern in the future. Most developers were dissatisfied with the code quality generated by the conversion tools and faced various issues when using the tools and handling the generated code. Figure 17 (in Appendix) provide detailed breakdown of the same.

Manual Refactoring. As shown in Figure 14 (in Appendix), developers reported spending significant effort in manually fixing the tool-generated code. Figure 13 (in Appendix) shows the distribution of categories of refactoring. Lifetime annotations and stylistic (i.e., idiomatic) changes are expected as noted in related works [27, 28]. The most common fixes (58.3%) involve handling complex C types and translating them to suitable RUST types, which contradicts the belief that manual effort is mainly needed for `unsafe` blocks.

Desired Tool Improvements. Our questions about desired tool improvements provided interesting findings. As targeted by recent efforts [8], the majority of developers want tools to produce more idiomatic RUST code (58.3%) and with fewer unsafe blocks (50%). A majority (58.3%) of developers expect conversion tools to handle type conversion – a known hard problem [66] for nested recursive types, especially in the presence of RUST lifetime semantics. The left side of Figure 13 (in the Appendix) shows the type of tool improvements desired by the corresponding percentage of developers.

Finding F9: *Most LLM-based tools require significant manual effort to decompose the C project into translatable subcomponents and to combine the translated RUST code back into a whole project.*

3.6 RQ 5: Evaluation Methodology

The *Original Evaluation* column of Table 1 shows our analysis of all tools.

Dataset (Ds): We use three aspects to categorize the dataset. Specifically, (i) *Type*: Standard dataset (📄), e.g., SPEC [37], Juliet [10], custom dataset (📄) or a mix of both (📄). (ii) *Number of Programs (NP)*. (iii) *Median Size (SLoC) of Programs (SzP)*. All tools use their own custom selection of programs on which to evaluate, except EvoC2RUST (📄), which uses Vivo-bench [1], in addition to their own closed-source dataset. However, as we will discuss in § 4.1, this is not adequate. In the absence of such a dataset, the tools use their own custom selection of programs, making comparisons challenging. *Evaluation Metrics (ME):* We check if the tools use some *standard* metrics to measure the effectiveness of their technique (indicated by M if they do, or M if they don't). While it is possible to measure some aspect of the conversion (e.g., number of `unsafe` blocks), it does not enable objective comparisons between tools. For example,

a tool creating more `unsafe` blocks might be preferable if it converts array pointers to safer RUST types, e.g., `Vec`.

Without standardized dataset and metrics, it is difficult to objectively compare the effectiveness of different approaches. This motivates the need for a representative dataset and comprehensive evaluation metrics, which we introduce in § 4.

Finding F10: *Developers claim tools are easy to set up, but face robustness issues in use.*

Finding F11: *Developers invest considerable effort fixing tool-generated code, primarily to convert complex C types to appropriate RUST types.*

Finding F12: *Developers expect conversion tools to handle type conversion automatically, but current tools fall short in this regard.*

Validating Produced RUST Code Conversion tools must ensure the validity and correctness of the generated RUST code, specifically that it is *syntactically valid and semantically equivalent* to the original C code. All tools check for syntactic validity using the RUST compiler and it can be improved further using linting tools, such as Clippy [6]. This is indicated by column SN in Table 1. A ✓ indicates that the tool uses only the compiler to verify syntactic validity. A ✓ indicates that the tool uses both the compiler and the linting tools. **Semantic Equivalence (SE):** Scalability is a known problem with classic formal methods [42]. In practice, researchers often rely on dynamic analysis techniques, like tests (indicated by Tc) or dynamic validation (indicated by Dv), which check input-output equivalence at function entry and exit. This is shown in column SE of Table 1. *Most tools use differential testing with test cases to verify the generated RUST code’s semantic validity by comparing its output against the original C code.* Only LAERTES additionally uses a cross-checking tool [4] that compares C and RUST execution traces, though this tool has been discontinued and is no longer supported.

Recently, a few tools have tried to perform semantic equivalence by using a common representation. Specifically, they convert the C and RUST code into a common representation and check for equivalence. For instance, RUSTASSURE uses WebAssembly and RUSTFLOW uses LLVM IR. However, these are LLM-based tools and work at a function-level, and their feasibility and effectiveness at the whole program level remains unexplored. *There is no work to formally verify the semantic equivalence between the original C code and the converted RUST code at whole program level.* The recent CRUX tool [59] provides a promising approach using LLVM IR.

Finding F13: *All tools use the compiler for syntactic validity and tests for semantic validity of the generated Rust code, yet none check for idiomatcity or recommended practices (e.g., through linters).*

Open Problem P3: *We need techniques to statically verify the semantic equivalence of C and corresponding RUST code at the whole program level. Recent techniques using LLVM IR, such as CRUX [59], could be used to explore possible solutions.*

4 CRUSTADE and CRETRICS

As discussed in § 3.6, there is no standard dataset and metrics for evaluating C-to-RUST conversion tools. There is a need for more comprehensive means to evaluate the C-to-RUST conversion techniques. A *representative dataset* and *metrics* are two necessary components for evaluation.

4.1 CRUSTADE: C-to-RUST Dataset

We argue that an effective dataset for evaluating C-to-RUST conversion tools must meet the following requirements. First, it should cover a wide range of C programming idioms, not just a narrow subset of features. Second, it should include programs with *complex C pointer usage*, often seen as a major challenge in translating C code to RUST [27]. Third, the dataset should have *real-world programs*, as these codebases typically show more complex and idiomatic C usage. Finally, it should allow for fine-grained assessment, such as identifying which function types are difficult to convert and which array pointers are transformed into higher-level RUST types. **Limitations of Existing Datasets.** We found that none of the existing datasets satisfy the above requirements. Table 2 provides an overview of representative existing datasets. The existing datasets primarily target LLM-based tools and therefore consist of small, single-file programs, respecting LLMs’ context limits. RustRepoTrans-C includes 145 programs extracted from two real-world projects, *i.e.*, `deltacore-chat` and `incubator-milagro-crypto`, but these programs correspond to individual target functions rather than complete applications. Furthermore, all of these contain single-file programs. CRUST-Bench [43] partially addresses these issues by including multi-file projects collected from various GitHub repositories. However, none of these are real-world utilities, *i.e.*, used on commodity systems. Also, none of the datasets include multi-threaded C programs, nor do they have any annotations. Finally, none of the datasets have any functional tests, which are important to test the functional correctness of the generated RUST code.

CRUSTADE Dataset. To address these shortcomings, we created a new dataset of diverse C programs covering various features, idioms, and application domains across 9 categories.

Diverse C language idioms: We gathered programs from an advanced C programming course at our university, consisting of 20 small programs (≤ 250 lines) exploring various C features, including recursive and nested data structures, and file, string, and bit manipulations. We also included larger real-world programs ($> 3K$ lines) from the C2RUST tool [5], covering a wide range of idiomatic C usage.

Complex C pointer usage: To capture challenging pointer-related constructs, we included programs from Ptrdist [9], which contain large C programs featuring complex pointer patterns, such as double and triple indirection, along with their associated usage scenarios. **Complex C features and multithreading:** GNU codebases often use complex C language features [30, 72], such as macros to mimic templates, multithreading, etc. We used programs from the GNU-Inetutils package [32], which includes large multithreaded programs that interact with files and networks. We also collected a few simpler (*i.e.*, single-threaded) GNU programs. Recent works [66, 67] indicate that embedded codebases differ from regular ones. Therefore, we also collected a FreeRTOS-based application.

Functions and Pointers Annotations. We manually analyzed each program and annotated every function based on its functionality type. For instance, we annotate a function parsing a string as *string-processing* (Sp). Specifically, we add the comment `// C2RDataset: FunctionType(numerical)` just before the function declaration. We identified 12 categories of functions and annotated each function accordingly. Previous work [27] shows that array pointers are challenging to tackle in RUST conversion. To assess this, we also

Table 2: Comparison of various C-to-Rust translation evaluation datasets.

S.No.	Dataset	N. Progs	SLOC		Multi-file	Application Types	Multi-threaded applications?	Functional Tests	Fine-grained Annotations
			Max / Mean						
1	Vivo-Bench [1]	19	626 / 340		✘	Real-World (0%) / Rest (100%)	✘	✘	✘
2	RustRepoTrans-C [55]	145	356 / 28		✘	Real-World (0%) / Rest (100%)	✘	✘	✘
3	TransCoder-Rust [74]	506	89 / 42		✘	Real-World (0%) / Rest (100%)	✘	✘	✘
4	CRUST-Bench [43]	100	25k / 958		✔	Real-World (0%) / Rest (100%)	✘	✘	✘
5	CRUSTADE (ours)	61	75k / 3862		✔	Real-World (57%) + Rest (43%)	✔	✔	✔

manually analyzed all pointers in all programs and annotated all array pointers (i.e., parameters, local variables, fields, and globals). These annotations enable fine-grained evaluation of the conversion tools, as will be discussed in § 4.2. The C code on the left of Listing 6 (in the Appendix) shows an example of these annotations.

In summary, we collected a total of 61 diverse C programs of various sizes. Based on the underlying functionality, we categorized each program into one of the 9 categories. The Table 3 summarizes our programs, their categories, and SLoCs. The *Types of Functions* column summarizes function types and the number of functions of each type across program categories. We streamlined the organization of all our programs (through CMakeLists.txt) such that every project can be built using a simple command (e.g., cmake debug) for Debug build) and similarly compile_command.json can also be generated using a single command.

Recently, the TRACTOR program [8] has begun developing a dataset [17], though it remains incomplete. Our dataset can complement this effort by providing function-level and array-level annotations, along with multi-threaded examples, enabling more fine-grained evaluation of tool failures.

4.2 CRETRICS: Evaluation Metrics

According to the principles of translation validation [60], the generated RUST code should be valid, maintainable, correct (w.r.t original C code), and improve memory security.

4.2.1 Motivation. As discussed in § 3.6, most existing tools use ad hoc metrics to evaluate the translated RUST code, primarily checking validity and correctness. For instance, C2RUST only checks if the converted RUST code compiles (i.e., validity) and tests pass (i.e., correctness). Other tools, such as CRUSTS and LAERTES, assess security by measuring the number of `unsafe` blocks. However, fewer number of `unsafe` blocks does not always imply more secure RUST code. Listing 1 shows an example that demonstrates this, where both functions are possible translations of the same C code. `less_unsafe_but_not_ok()` contains only one `unsafe` block, but it has an out-of-bounds access bug (indicated by `⚡`), when `idx` exceeds the length of `arr`. In contrast, the `more_unsafe_but_ok()` has two `unsafe` blocks, but avoids this bug, as RUST's runtime bounds checking will prevent the invalid access (indicated by `🛡`).

One obvious metric is *Gross Memory Safety* (GMS), i.e., how many memory corruption vulnerabilities in the original C code are prevented in the converted RUST code. We assessed this using 1.2k programs with memory corruption vulnerabilities from the Juliet C Test suite [10], converting each to RUST with all the tools

```

1 use std::mem::ManuallyDrop;
2 static mut N: i32 = 100;
3 fn more_unsafe_but_ok(
4     arr: *mut i32, len: usize, idx: usize) -> i32 {
5     // unsafe #1
6     let v = unsafe {
7         ManuallyDrop::new(
8             Vec::from_raw_parts(arr, len, len) );
9     // unsafe #2
10    let to_add = unsafe { N };
11    🛡 v[idx] + to_add
12 }
13 fn less_unsafe_but_not_ok(
14     arr: *mut i32, len: usize,
15     idx: usize, to_add: i32) -> i32 {
16     // unsafe #1
17     let ith = unsafe { *arr.add(idx) ⚡ };
18     ith + to_add
19 }

```

Listing 1: Less `unsafe` blocks \Rightarrow more secure.

and checking whether the original vulnerability persisted. Unfortunately, none of the converted RUST code prevented the original vulnerabilities. Beyond this result, GMS has broader limitations: it requires knowing all vulnerabilities in the C code apriori, which is unrealistic in practice. Furthermore, GMS does not capture security hardening e.g., replacing `unsafe` (but non-vulnerable) C library calls with safe RUST counterparts. We need metrics that can holistically assess the converted RUST code relative to the original C code.

Finding F14: Current C-to-RUST conversion tools failed to prevent any spatial memory vulnerabilities in Juliet C Test suite, indicating that simply converting C-to-RUST does not guarantee memory safety. We propose CRETRICS, a set of metrics to comprehensively assess generated RUST code, organized into three primary groups as shown in Figure 2, each containing one or more metrics.

Figure 2: CRETRICS Organization.

Setup. We selected tools that were practical to use (i.e., require reasonable user effort). For instance, we did not select any of the Manual Combination Tools (Table 1), as each tool required custom decomposition (i.e., splitting the C program) and combination (i.e.,

Table 3: CRUSTADE Dataset. (SP:StringProcessing, AP:ArrayProcessing, DSP:DataStructureProcessing, NP:Numerical, FA:FileAccess, Sr:StdioAccess, NA:NetworkAccess, WR:Wrapper, VL:Validation, ASM:Assembly, RM:RawMemory, SC:SyscallWrapper)

Application Type	Num. Progs.	Types of Functions												Size (SLOC)		
		SP	AP	DSP	NP	FA	St	NA	Wr	VL	ASM	RM	SC	Mean	Median	Max
Algorithms (Al)	11	3	42	60	8	12	28	0	21	8	0	0	0	259	171	1,111
DataStructure (Ds)	5	5	8	34	1	12	11	0	19	15	0	0	0	232	279	303
Embedded (EMB)	1	5	34	135	10	0	6	0	65	31	12	1	0	16,892	16,892	16,892
File Processing (Fp)	3	1	3	0	0	4	5	0	2	1	0	0	0	64	68	72
Network Clients (Nc)	15	194	113	233	36	28	248	63	204	72	0	0	3	2,042	1,121	8,671
Network Servers (Ns)	10	134	33	120	3	68	40	47	60	34	0	0	21	2,048	1,588	5,922
Pointer Benchmarks (PTR)	3	16	62	78	23	5	41	0	17	8	0	0	0	2,159	551	5,572
String Processing (Sp)	5	257	157	490	132	49	87	0	263	199	0	8	1	21,528	7,029	75,648
Utilities (UTIL)	8	217	155	249	50	42	67	0	148	58	0	2	6	6,159	2,212	24,339
Total	61	834	607	1,399	263	220	533	110	799	426	12	11	31			

the generated RUST code) steps, which required significant manual effort. We ran these tools on our CRUSTADE dataset and evaluated them using our CRETRICS metrics. Most of the tools were not easy to set up and run. We had to manually fix several of these tools to make them work. We provide more details in Appendix A.6.

4.2.2 I. Foundations of Correctness. To begin with, it is essential to ensure that the translation is usable and functional. This involves ensuring that it compiles seamlessly and adheres to C language behavior as verified through existing tests. This establishes a foundation for conducting deeper analysis and further improvements.

Syntactic Validity. The generated RUST code should be syntactically valid. Syntactically invalid code is unusable because it will not compile. We use the RUST compiler to check this. *We expect the converted code to be syntactically valid, i.e., compile successfully.*

Our results show that *none of the tools were successful in producing syntactically valid code for all programs in our dataset.* The range of failures varies from 45%-100% of programs. C2RUST (with the least number of failures) failed to produce valid RUST code for 45% of the programs, which includes all network clients and servers. TYMCRAT and EVOC2RUST fail to produce valid code for *any* of the programs. Advanced tools (that work on top of C2RUST) often regress and fail for additional programs. Finally, *none of the tools work on embedded programs, confirming the observation made by Sharma et al. in their recent work [66].* We provide more details of this analysis in Appendix A.3.

Functional Correctness. The generated RUST code should be functionally equivalent to the original C code – a necessary requirement. We rely on *dynamic functional equivalence* checking. For a given input, we check if the RUST code produces the same output as the corresponding C code. We use the existing test suites of original C programs and *expect all tests across all suites to pass, and any failures indicate potential functional non-equivalence.*

The syntactically valid code produced by all tools (except for NOPCRAT and C2SAFERRUST) was functionally correct for most programs. C2SAFERRUST produced syntactically valid but semantically incorrect code for handling program arguments. NOPCRAT did not correctly update the callsites for some functions for which it had

updated signatures. One of the programs, ft (an algorithms program), uses undefined behavior (e.g., integer overflow) as part of its functionality. The corresponding RUST code panicked on testcases, triggering those undefined behaviors (a valid and expected case of the program). Developers should be careful of programs that use such undefined behavior, while converting them to RUST. We provide more details of our analysis in Appendix A.4.

Open Problem P4: *We need techniques to determine whether a program relies on C undefined behaviors (e.g., integer overflows) as part of its intended semantics and, therefore, for functional correctness. Such behavior must be preserved during translation to RUST*

4.2.3 II. Security & Safety Enhancements. In addition to usability considerations, we assess the extent to which RUST's safety features are effectively realized in the translation process. This evaluation reveals a reduction in both the number and justification of unsafe regions, an increase in the use of bounded and reference types, and a replacement of potentially hazardous C library calls.

Residual Unsafety. As discussed in § 2, **unsafe** annotations permit certain memory-unsafe operations, which can lead to memory safety vulnerabilities (e.g., spatial safety vulnerabilities) [48], which are not possible in safe RUST code. *The converted RUST code must not have any unsafe annotations to ensure memory safety.* As noted in § 3.5, **unsafe** usage in generated RUST code was also a major concern among survey respondents.

We use a RUST compiler plugin (inspired by QRATES [18]) to identify **unsafe** regions and categorize them according to the underlying reason. We only analyzed syntactically valid RUST code produced by the tools. C2RUST, by default, marks every function as **unsafe** and other tools attempt to improve this by tackling specific unsafe idioms (e.g., LAERTES tries to convert raw pointers to references). Figure 3 shows the percentage of **unsafe** functions in the RUST code produced by tools across different program categories. The mark indicates that the corresponding tool did not produce valid RUST code for all programs in that category. Despite the improvements, advanced tools, specifically CROWN, CONCRAT, NOPCRAT and C2SAFERRUST, failed to produce safe functions across all categories. While C2SAFERRUST appears to reduce the **unsafe** code, the code produced is functionally incorrect for most programs. LAERTES'

Figure 3: Unsafe Functions by Program Type

apparent reduction in unsafe functions stems from introducing safe helper functions ("Extra" category) rather than refactoring existing unsafe code. As shown in Figure 7 (in Appendix), high unsafety persists across all primary categories. *Does this mean the existing tools fail to improve unsafe code? No.*

Tools tend to tackle individual aspects of unsafety. For *e.g.*, CROWN aims to reduce raw pointer dereferences in RUST code, and thus generates fewer functions which are unsafe due to *Deref of Raw Pointers*. However, a function can be unsafe due to multiple reasons simultaneously, *e.g.*, both accessing raw pointers and modifying global variables (Listing 1). Consequently, even if a tool improves one aspect, functions remain unsafe if they contain other patterns. Interestingly, across all tools, there were a significant number of functions unnecessarily marked as *unsafe*: C2RUST marks all functions as unsafe by default, and other tools (except CRUSTS) do not attempt to remove these. Table 7 (in Appendix) shows the reasons for unsafe functions across different tools. *One way to improve this would be to combine existing tools in an iterative daisy chain manner until all unsafe blocks are removed.* However, as discussed in *Syntactic Validity*, tools have regressions and varying degrees of failure. Hence, combining them could be detrimental and less effective.

Pointer Conversion. As mentioned in § 4.2.1, the number of *unsafe* blocks is not an accurate metric of memory safety, and other metrics (like GMS) are idealistic and inapplicable to realistic use cases. Moreover, GMS is coarse and fails to capture fine-grained security improvements, such as the use of higher-order RUST types (*e.g.*, `Vec`), which improves safety through bounds checking and lifetimes.

We observe that pointers and arrays are the root cause of spatial and temporal memory safety vulnerabilities in C. Converting a pointer to a reference or bounded object in RUST eliminates potential safety issues through static and runtime checking. We therefore argue that measuring *Pointer Conversion*, *i.e.*, how pointers are converted to bounded objects or references provides a reasonable estimate of the memory safety improvements.

For each program, we check how many pointers *can* be converted to bounded types and how many are actually converted by the tool. We expect all array-pointers to be converted to *bounded types*, *i.e.*, a reference (*e.g.*, a slice `&T[...]`), or a bounded type (*e.g.*, a `Vec`). For each program, we check how many array pointers are converted to bounded objects, which gives us **Expected Bounded (ExB)**. Array pointers that are not converted to bounded types are **Unexpected Unbounded ($UxUB$)**. Some tools (*e.g.*, LAERTES, CROWN) claim to convert regular (*i.e.*, non-array) pointers to bounded types, specifically references. Tools can also introduce additional raw pointers. To assess this, we capture the number of regular pointers converted to bounded types (**Unexpected Bounded (UxB)**), which stayed as raw pointers (**Expected Unbounded ($ExUB$)**), and additional raw pointers (**Additional Raw (RUB)**) introduced by the tool. We get array pointers information for each C program via a source-level pass, identifying the annotations (§ 4.1). We identify regular pointers through a CLANG pass. These are matched context-sensitively against the corresponding RUST code via an HIR Pass to compute the above metrics.

*For improved spatial and temporal safety, we want a relatively high number of bounded objects (*i.e.*, high values for ExB , UxB) and low (or no) unbounded types (*i.e.*, low values for $UxUB$, $ExUB$, RUB).*

Figure 4 shows how tools converted array pointers (**Bounded: ExB , Unbounded: $UxUB$**) across programs categories. The 0 bars indicate that the tool failed to convert all programs in that category, *e.g.*, CRUSTS on datastructure. While shows some array pointers converted to bounded types (ExB), after investigation, we found that *these are just static arrays (*e.g.*, `int arr[4];`) which can be trivially converted to RUST arrays (*e.g.*, `let arr: [int; 4]`). No tool converted dynamic arrays (*e.g.*, `int *arr;`) to appropriate RUST types. Differences in total array pointer counts across tools is because we computed the metrics on only syntactically valid translations. For instance, CONCRAT was able to translate only one `ptrdist` program (ks), which had only static arrays, yielding 100% ExB for that category. C2SAFERRUST performs better in this aspect, but failed to produce functionally correct code for most of the programs.*

In most cases, non-array pointers remain raw, though in certain categories (`ptrdist` and `utilities`), some are converted to references. All tools introduce many raw pointers due to templated idioms used for converting C pointer constructs. *We also observed instances where non-array pointers were converted to references to raw pointers, accessed by dereferencing the internal raw pointer, which does not enhance memory safety.* Figure 8 (in Appendix) indicates the number of converted non-array pointers, and additional raw pointers introduced by the tools. Despite differences in the number of *unsafe* blocks, all tools perform similarly in pointer conversions, confirming the utility of these metrics and corroborating our findings with the Juliet Test Suite (§ 4.2.1).

Finding F15: *While most existing tools focus on reducing unsafe, particularly due to raw pointers, our findings in § 3.5 show that type conversion constitutes the dominant source of manual developer effort*

Handling External Calls. Replacing C external library calls with RUST counterparts improves security by preventing vulnerabilities in the corresponding C library, *e.g.*, replacing `libc`'s `getenv` with RUST's `std::env::var`. For each program, we measure percentage of external library calls replaced with calls to RUST standard library

Figure 4: Array Pointers Conversion (ExB vs UxUB)

or crates, where a higher percentage indicates improved security. We use source-level passes and binary analysis scripts to perform this matching. Our results indicate that no tool, except CONCRAT and C2SAFERRUST, replaces external library calls with safer RUST variants, not even standard library calls, such as `libc`. CONCRAT aims to replace C lock API with RUST one. C2SAFERRUST replaces some file operations API calls with the RUST standard library, and also reduces memory API calls. However, as noted earlier, C2SAFERRUST's output fails functional tests for most programs. Listing 5 (in Appendix) shows an example of external calls in converted RUST code.

4.2.4 III. *Quality & Maintainability.* We evaluate whether the output is idiomatic and maintainable.

Code Quality. To ensure maintainability, the generated RUST code must be high quality, well-formatted, and follow idiomatic RUST standards. We use `clippy` [6], the most common linter in the RUST ecosystem, to assess code quality. We expect high-quality code with minimal `clippy` warnings. We ran `clippy` only on syntactically valid code produced by each tool. All valid programs had one or more stylistic issues, which is expected as most existing tools do not prioritize code quality. Prevalent stylistic issues remain consistent across different program types for a given tool, but differ across tools on the same program. Table 6 (in Appendix) provides more information.

Finding F16: Existing tools fail to handle complex codebases and do not always produce syntactically valid code. Advanced tools that develop over C2RUST frequently regress and make incorrect modifications to the valid RUST code produced by C2RUST.

Finding F17: Existing tools, despite individual improvements, do not enhance overall safety, as real-world functions exhibit multiple unsafe idioms.

Finding F18: Existing C-to-RUST conversion tools fail to convert dynamic array pointers to appropriate RUST types (e.g., `Vec`).

Finding F19: Existing tools add a significant number of extra raw pointers in the converted RUST code, possibly raising security risk.

Finding F20: Existing tools fail to replace external library calls in C with safer variants in the RUST code.

Open Problem P5: Tools tackle different unsafe idioms. We need a way to constructively combine them into a conversion ensemble that enables safer Rust code – naively combining all tools risks regressions and reduced effectiveness.

Open Problem P6: We need techniques to replace calls to c external library functions with safer variants in RUST.

5 Threats to Validity

While our CRETRICS metrics (§ 4.2) aim to cover various aspects, they are not complete. For instance, these metrics do not address the formal semantic equivalence of the converted RUST code. However, our metrics effectively capture improvements in maintainability and memory safety.

Functional tests in CRUSTADE rely on existing application test suites, which may be insufficient. Techniques like fuzzing can help enhance these suites. Our dataset includes only one embedded application, limiting generalizability. Recent research by Sharma *et al.* [66] indicates that C-to-RUST conversion tools often struggle with embedded codebases. Additionally, developer survey results may be biased by voluntary participation and self-reported responses, which may not reflect the general security posture.

6 Related Work

Several works [20, 29, 74] aim to convert C code to RUST. In this work, we focus on C-to-RUST conversion tools and techniques.

Evaluating Code Translation. There are studies evaluating the effectiveness of code translation techniques. One related work is by Xia *et al.* [79], who conducted an empirical study of C2RUST [12] to understand challenges in translating automatically generated C code using CSMITH [82]. However, they focus mainly on C2RUST, using automatically generated C programs, which are not representative of real-world applications. Pan *et al.* [56] systematically studied bugs introduced by LLM-based translators across C, C++, Go, Java, and Python, identifying 15 recurring error categories and proposing a prompt-engineering technique to reduce them.

Developer Studies on RUST. Many RUST studies [33, 38, 47] are related to the use of unsafe blocks. Recently, Sharma *et al.* [66] analyzed developers' perspectives on RUST for embedded systems and identified various interesting findings and open problems. There exists no explicit study on understanding developers' perspective on C-to-RUST conversion. Recently, Li *et al.* [45] performed an analysis of manually converted RUST code from 33 participants and found various interesting findings. In this work, we perform the first comprehensive survey to understand developer perspectives on various aspects of C-to-RUST conversion.

7 Conclusions

We performed the first systematic study of C-to-RUST conversion techniques, highlighting their metrics, drawbacks, and open problems. We also created the CRUSTADE dataset (61 real-world annotated C programs) and CRETRICS metrics for comprehensive evaluation of C-to-RUST techniques. Furthermore, we also performed a developer study to understand their perspectives on C-to-RUST conversion and expectations from automated tools. Our findings shed light on future research directions for C-to-RUST.

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A Appendix

A.1 LLM based C-to-RUST conversion tools requiring manual combination.

Ideally a user would expect to provide the original C source code alongwith the build script and get a single combined RUST project, having appropriate Cargo.toml and build.rs (if required) files to build the project. While the multi-stage approach taken by LLM tools looks promising, the tools are currently not usable – they require considerable user effort and the end-result doesn’t often compile. Most tools involve some manual pre-structuring steps. RUSTMAP [22] requires the user to translate the macros manually and place the translations in a pre-defined folder structure, before the tool can even start processing the project. SACTOR [87] can only work on a single C file and requires the user to combine the entire project into a single C input file. RUSTFLOW [84] requires the project to be modified to follow a certain folder structure and requires that the user provide a JSON file corresponding to each C source file, describing its various attributes. These requirements make these tools impractical for working on real-world codebases.

Moreover, the task of combining the different translated units is largely left to the user. As we discuss in Appendix A.5, the different translated units might have some semantic differences, making it impossible to combine them in an automated manner – a limitation that is shared by most LLM tools (RUSTMAP, RUSTASSURE [19], VERT [81]). This further makes these tools impractical to use. Table 4 provides an overview of these tools.

These tools investigated various interesting approaches *e.g.*, FLUORINE investigated different feedback strategies for the repair phase (simple restart, hinted restart, counter-example guide repair). They made an interesting finding – *restarting the translation process with the original prompt was more effective than providing counter-examples to the LLM for repair*. However, the tools still fail to produce valid code for most cases.

In the case of LLM tools, failures can happen at two levels: file (translation unit) and project level. For a particular translation unit, LLM may produce RUST code that is syntactically incorrect, like missing imports, or uses non-existent (hallucinated) APIs. Even if individual RUST files compile, it might be difficult to link them together because of conflicting symbols, incompatible types, and type discrepancies across multiple translation units. For *e.g.*, in one translation unit, a C enum might be translated to a RUST enum but in another translation unit, it might be replaced by constants. Moreover there are semantic differences between C and RUST that may yield RUST files that compile but are different from the C translation unit. For *e.g.*, as enums in C are like grouped integer constants, multiple variants are allowed to have the same value. However, in RUST, two enum variants cannot have the same value. Hence LLM might decide not to enable one of them in the RUST code. The resulting code may compile, but it would be semantically different.

The current divide-and-conquer approach adopted by LLM tools works well when parts are mostly independent and easy to join [52, 85]. But recent studies show it struggles when there are strong links between parts or when errors happen during merging (called "aggregator noise") [23, 35, 88]. In program translation, these problems are common: translating parts separately often makes the model guess global types from local code, causing duplicated or mismatched type definitions and incompatible function signatures.

A.2 RUST Background

Listing 2 shows an example with a potential out-of-bounds access (🚨). The RUST compiler adds a runtime check and causes the program to panic during runtime if the value of `idx` is not within the bounds of `arr`.

RUST achieves temporal memory safety [54] by enforcing single Ownership [11, 15] and valid lifetimes.

Ownership. An object can have a single owner, *i.e.*, variable, *e.g.*, in Listing 2, `o` owns the `String` object allocated at line 5. Similarly, `r` owns the object allocated at line 10. The ownership can be transferred from one variable to another, *e.g.*, the assignment at line 16 in Listing 2 transfers the ownership of the object from `o` to `c`. Once the ownership is transferred, the original variables cannot be used and will be prevented by the compiler. As indicated by 🚫 in Listing 2, the compiler will throw an error at the use of the variable `o` at line 18, as the ownership is transferred to `c`. Once the owner goes out-of-scope,

```

1  #[cfg(feature = "bar")]
2  fn foo() {
3      let mut arr: [i32; 10] = [10; 10];
4      let s: &str;
5      let o: String = String::from("hello");
6
7      let idx = // User input
8      🚨arr[idx] = 0; // Runtime panic if
9                          // idx is out of bounds.
10     {
11         let r = String::from("world");
12         s = r.as_str(); // s is a reference to r
13     } // r goes out of scope.
14     // Compiler error: lifetime violation
15     println!("{}", s); // s references
16                          // invalid object(r)
17
18     let c = o; // Ownership of string is
19                // transferred to c
20     // Compiler error: Ownership violation
21     println!("{}", o); // o no longer owns
22                          // the string.
23 }

```

Listing 2: Rust ownership, lifetimes, run-time checks and configuration.

the corresponding memory is automatically freed (*i.e.*, dropped). RUST compiler adds the necessary deallocation code. For example, in Listing 2, once `r` goes out of scope (at line 12) the corresponding object (allocated at line 10) owned by it will be deallocated.

References and Lifetimes. RUST allows references (mutable or immutable) which can be used to *Borrow* a reference to an object. Specifically, borrowing allows multiple variables to reference a single object, *e.g.*, in Listing 2 `s` is an immutable reference (created at line 11) to the object owned by `r`. However, at any given program point, RUST allows only a single mutable reference to a memory location. The Lifetime semantics [14, 58] prevent references to out-of-scope objects. Specifically, references and memory objects have lifetimes, and the RUST compiler ensures that references do not outlive the original memory object. In Listing 2, as indicated by 🚫, the compiler throws an error at line 14 as the reference `s` outlives that corresponding object, which goes out-of-scope and is deallocated at line 12.

A.3 Syntactic Validity

As discussed in § 4.2.2, the converted code should be syntactically valid. Figure 5 shows the summary of results for all tools. The percentage under the tool (on x-axis) shows the percentage of programs on which the tool failed, and numbers on individual bars show the raw numbers, and the sizes of bars are normalized to the total percentage.

These syntactic errors are not always easy to fix and might require considerable effort (as mentioned in § 3.5). As mentioned in § 3.3, most tools (except for TYMCRA and EVO C2RUST) work on top of C2RUST and consequently also inherit its failures. In addition, these tools also fail for additional programs, *e.g.*, 67% (for CROWN) v/s 45% (for C2RUST). *This situation is especially pronounced in CRUSTS, which failed on 83% (38% regressions) of programs. Although TYMCRA (an LLM based tool) is able to process all programs, none of the conversions are syntactically valid. This is expected*

Table 4: Summary of C-to-Rust conversion tools which are not automated and require considerable manual effort.

S.No.	Tool	Goal	Conversion Methodology Sec. 3.3			Software Aspects Sec. 3.4		Validity of Conversion Sec. 3.6		Original Evaluation Sec. 3.6				Usability Sec. 3.5		
			APPR	INSt	INVE	GENB	CONF	SN	SE	Ds	NP	SzP	ME	SU	RN	INP
Manual Composition Tools																
1	RUSTMAP [22]	Idiomatic Rust	LM	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	Tc	☰	>20	≤1k	M	🟢	▶	👤
2	RUSTASSURE [19]	Idiomatic Rust	LM	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗	☰	≤10	≤1k	M	🟢	▶	👤
3	RUSTFLOW [84]	Idiomatic Rust	LM	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	Tc ⚠	☰	>20	≤1k	M	🟢	▶	👤
4	SACTOR [87]	Idiomatic Rust	LM	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	Tc	☰	>20	≤1k	M	🟢	▶	👤
5	VERT [81]	Idiomatic Rust	LM	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	Dv ⚠	☰	>20	≤1k	M	🟢	▶	👤
6	FLUORINE [81]	Idiomatic Rust	LM	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	Dv ⚠	☰	>20	≤1k	M	🟢	▶	👤

⚠ Only done on individual translation unit level.

Figure 5: Summary of Syntactic Errors in RUST code produced by conversion tools. (Numbers inside the bars are the number of programs that are not syntactically valid)

as the original paper claims that producing valid code is not TYMCRAT’s goal. All LLM tools often fail due to generating incompatible types even for the simple types, e.g., mixing `u32` and `i32`. This is a result of the semantic disconnect between the translated units that results from processing the units separately through LLMs, which are inherently non-deterministic. We provide more details in Appendix A.5.

Table 5: Abbreviations of common Clippy warnings.

Clippy Warning	Description
UNR	Unneeded ‘return’ statement
SNE	Statement with no effect
ZAM	‘0 as *mut _’ detected
UMS	Unsafe function’s docs miss ‘# Safety’ section
RLB	Returning the result of a ‘let’ binding from a block
DAD	Deref which would be done by auto-deref
DRP	This public function might dereference a raw pointer but is not marked ‘unsafe’
BES	This boolean expression can be simplified

A.4 Functional Correctness Issues

Similarly to code quality metrics, we performed functionality tests on only syntactically valid programs. Figure 6 shows the summary of functional correctness failures. The percentage under the tool (in the x-axis) shows the percentage of valid programs with functionality issues, and numbers on individual bars show the number of incorrect and correct programs generated in that category by the corresponding tool. The sizes of the bars are normalized to the total percentage of failures by the corresponding tool.

For one of the algorithm programs (`ft`), the RUST code produced by all tools failed a test. The `ft` program has a function to create random numbers, which uses integer overflow as part of its valid functionality. However, the corresponding RUST code panicked on one of the test cases, triggering the integer overflow as such overflow checks are inserted in debug builds of RUST programs.

We found that NOPCRAT failed for 28% of syntactically valid programs as it fails to correctly update the callsites (and other dependent locations) of the functions it modifies.

A.5 Semantic disconnect between individual translations

As mentioned earlier, LLM based tools typically take a divide-and-conquer approach. Translating separate units independently can

Table 6: Clippy Warnings for Stylistic Issues in the RUST code generated by various tools. (Details of abbreviations provided in Table 5)

Tool	Total	AL	Ds	EMB	Fp	Nc	Ns	Ptr	Sp	UTIL	Top Warnings
C2RUST	4,209	12.38%	3.59%		0.78%			16.16%	23.14%	43.95%	
		UNR (38.8%)	UNR (49.7%)	NA	UNR (75.8%)	NA	NA	ZAM (29.9%)	RLB (34.7%)	UNR (39.4%)	UNR (30.34%)
CROWN	1,442	30.51%	7.70%		2.70%			38.14%		20.94%	
		UNR (37.0%)	UNR (32.4%)	NA	UNR (64.1%)	NA	NA	ZAM (29.1%)	NA	UNR (33.1%)	UNR (29.68%)
LAERTES	4,381	13.95%	5.25%		1.99%			15.84%	24.81%	38.16%	
		UNR (33.7%)	UNR (33.5%)	NA	ZAM (52.9%)	NA	NA	ZAM (28.0%)	RLB (31.1%)	DAD (43.5%)	DAD (18.42%)
CRUSTS	639	94.99%			5.01%						
		DRP (28.0%)	NA	NA	UNR (53.1%)	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	UNR (28.95%)
CONCRAT	1,346	42.57%	17.68%		2.90%			12.04%		24.81%	
		ZAM (46.4%)	ZAM (68.5%)	NA	ZAM (48.7%)	NA	NA	ZAM (65.4%)	BES (12.3%)	SNE (39.8%)	ZAM (46.73%)
NOPCRAT	3,085	16.99%	4.89%		1.10%			5.25%	33.03%	38.74%	
		UNR (38.5%)	UNR (49.7%)	NA	UNR (73.5%)	NA	NA	ZAM (30.9%)	RLB (33.2%)	UNR (48.1%)	UNR (33.39%)
C2SAFERRUST	1,206	22.97%	7.79%		1.41%			44.69%	12.44%	10.70%	
		UNR (20.2%)	UNR (27.7%)	NA	UNR (35.3%)	NA	NA	ZAM (21.0%)	UUB* (26.7%)	SNE (38.0%)	ZAM (16.58%)
		ZAM (15.5%)	ZAM (22.3%)	NA	UPR* (11.8%)	NA	NA	UUB* (11.9%)	UOP* (17.3%)	LEF* (15.5%)	SNE (14.51%)

lead to different translations for the same item, because the LLM does not have the whole program context. Moreover, the output of LLMs is not deterministic, and therefore they inherently can produce different translations for the same item in different runs. This *semantic disconnect* in the translated RUST code makes it non-trivial to merge the different translated units into a combined program. As a result, these tools have limited practical use. Listing 3 shows an example of the same C enum being converted differently in different translation units of the same program.

A.6 Issues Running Conversion Tools

TYMCRAT does not contain documentation on how to run the tool. Their scripts require an OpenAI API key, and that too in a particular file. The tool requires a set of arguments to be passed to it, without which it panics. Moreover, they ignore all entries in the `compile_commands.json` file which does not have `cc` as the compiler. Also, if the compile commands contain absolute paths, the tool ignores processing those files as well. None of these requirements/assumptions is documented anywhere. We had to read their source code and debug its working to unearth these requirements and peculiarities.

NOPCRAT does not provide any documentation for running the tool. It requires a certain flag, without which it would only analyze the program but would not translate it to RUST. This was also not indicated anywhere.

CONCRAT requires that the input C programs be processed through `cil` [2] before being provided as input to C2RUST. It also did not have any documentation about this either. For many of the programs in our dataset, it was also necessary to modify the translated RUST code produced by the tools to add certain unstable features, in order to get the output to compile.

C2SAFERRUST overrides the RUSTFLAGS before testing whether an application is compilable or not. This means that if the application requires additional flags, C2SAFERRUST will incorrectly consider it as a non-compilable application.

The missing instructions regarding the requirements for running the tools hinder their widespread adoption.

A.7 Incorrect macro expansion

Inadequate conversion of C macros to RUST can lead to decreased maintainability, loss of functionality, and incorrect code. Three kind of macros are most common in C code – function-like macro (`MAX(a,b)`), conditional compilation (based on `#ifdef DEBUG`) and predefined macros (`__DATE__` and `__TIME__`). The function-like macro are expanded at the call site. This *decreases the maintainability* of the converted RUST code. Any change in the macro will have to be updated at all translated call sites. For conditional compilation related macros, the translation removes any code that is conditionally disabled at the time of translation. This leads to *loss of functionality*. For *e.g.*, consider a C codebase that supports both Windows and Linux via conditional compilation constructs. If this C code was translated to RUST code on a Linux host, the translated RUST code would support only Linux, as the parts of code related to Windows would be removed during translation. Moreover, the predefined macros are not translated correctly. For example, if the original C code uses `__TIME__` macro, the intention would have been to use the time at which the code was being compiled. However, after conversion, the `__TIME__` macro would be replaced by the time at which the code was translated. This leads to *incorrect code*.

Some C preprocessor features do not have an equivalent in RUST. For *e.g.*, while one can define RUST macros, which could closely be inline to their `#define` counterparts in C, there does not exist any way to get the equivalent of `#undef`.

<pre> 1741 1 enum Category 1742 2 { 1743 3 Scheme = 0x01, 1744 4 Unreserved = 0x02, 1745 5 GenDelim = 0x04, 1746 6 SubDelim = 0x08, 1747 7 PCharSlash = 0x10, 1748 8 HexDigit = 0x20, 1749 9 Query = 0x40, 1750 10 Fragment = 0x80, 1751 11 Userinfo = 0x80, 1752 12 IPv6Char = 0x100, 1753 13 }; </pre>	<pre> 1741 1 enum Category { 1742 2 Scheme = 0x01, 1743 3 Unreserved = 0x02, 1744 4 GenDelim = 0x04, 1745 5 SubDelim = 0x08, 1746 6 PCharSlash = 0x10, 1747 7 HexDigit = 0x20, 1748 8 Query = 0x40, 1749 9 Fragment = 0x80, // Assigned a 1750 10 // different value 1751 11 Userinfo = 0x100, 1752 12 IPv6Char = 0x200, 1753 13 }; </pre>	<pre> 1741 1 struct Category; 1742 2 1743 3 impl Category { 1744 4 const SCHEME: u32 = 0x01; 1745 5 const UNRESERVED: u32 = 0x02; 1746 6 const GEN_DELIM: u32 = 0x04; 1747 7 const SUB_DELIM: u32 = 0x08; 1748 8 const PCHAR_SLASH: u32 = 0x10; 1749 9 const HEX_DIGIT: u32 = 0x20; 1750 10 const QUERY: u32 = 0x40; 1751 11 const FRAGMENT: u32 = 0x80; 1752 12 const USERINFO: u32 = 0x80; 1753 13 const IPV6_CHAR: u32 = 0x100; 1754 14 }; </pre>
(a) Enum in original C code	(b) Rust output in one translation unit.	(c) Rust output in another translation unit.

Listing 3: Example showing semantically different conversion in different translation units (RUSTASSURE).

<pre> 1756 typedef struct url_data { 1757 char *whole_url; 1758 const char *protocol; 1759 const char *userinfo; 1760 const char *host; 1761 const char *port; 1762 const char *path; 1763 const struct url_key_value *query; 1764 const char *fragment; 1765 } url_data_t; 1766 1767 #define GET_MEMBER(member) \ 1768 do { \ 1769 url_data_t *data = url_parse(url); \ 1770 char *out = data && data->member \ 1771 ? strdup(data->member) : NULL; \ 1772 url_free(data); \ 1773 return out; \ 1774 } while (0) 1775 1776 char *url_get_userinfo(const char *url) { 1777 GET_MEMBER(userinfo); 1778 } </pre>	<pre> 1756 macro_rules! GET_MEMBER { (\$member:ident) => 1757 { 1758 { 1759 let data = url_parse(url); 1760 let out = if let Some(data) = data { 1761 if let Some(member) = data.\$member { 1762 Some(strdup(member)) 1763 } else { None } 1764 } else { None }; 1765 url_free(data); 1766 out 1767 } 1768 } 1769 } 1770 1771 pub(crate) use GET_MEMBER; 1772 1773 pub fn url_get_userinfo(mut url: Ptr<u8>) -> Ptr<u8> { 1774 let data = url_parse(); 1775 let out = if let Some(data) = data { 1776 data 1777 } else { NULL!() }; 1778 url_free(); 1779 out 1780 } </pre>
(a) Original macro definition and usage	(b) Incorrect macro transformation

Listing 4: EvoC2Rust failure in transforming macro usage

Figure 6: Functional Correctness Statistics.

An example of an incorrect macro conversion by EvoC2Rust is given in Listing 4. The first listing shows the original macro definition as well as a call site of that macro. In the transformed

code, the macro definition remains semantically equivalent, but instead of using this new macro, EvoC2Rust expands the macro at the call location. The expansion itself is incorrect. Instead of returning a pointer to the userinfo member of the struct, it returns a pointer to the first member of the struct. As can be seen from the C definition, userinfo is the third member of the struct. Moreover, EvoC2Rust failed to generate definitions for url_parse and url_data_t, meaning the expanded macro uses a nonexistent function and struct.

Figure 7: Unsafe Functions by Function Type.

```

1891
1892
1893 1 extern "C" {
1894 2 fn strcmp(_: *const libc::c_char, _: *const libc::c_char) -> libc::c_int;
1895 3 }
1896 4
1897 5 #[no_mangle]
1898 6 pub unsafe extern "C" fn may_access_filename(
1899 7     mut name: *const libc::c_char,
1900 8     ) -> libc::c_char {
1901 9     ...
1902 10     if (... ||
1903 11         strcmp(name, b".\0" as *const u8 as *const libc::c_char) == 0
1904 12     )
1905 13     ...
1906 14 }

```

Listing 5: Example demonstrating libc external call present in converted RUST code C2RUST

A.8 Reasons for functions to be unsafe

Table 7 provides detailed breakdown of reasons why functions are unsafe across different tools.

A.9 Pointer Conversion

Figure 8 provides details about non-array pointer conversion.

```

1915 1 typedef struct genann {
1916 2     ...
1917 3     // C2RDataset: ArrayField(output)
1918 4     double *output;
1919 5     // C2RDataset: ArrayField(delta)
1920 6     double *delta;
1921 7     ...
1922 8 } genann;
1923 9
1924 10 //C2RDataset: FunctionType(stringprocessing, stdioaccess)
1925 11 static void makeargv (void)
1926 12 {
1927 13     //C2RDataset: CharacterArrayLocalVariable(cp)
1928 14     register char *cp;
1929 15     //C2RDataset: ArrayLocalVariable(argv)
1930 16     register char **argv = margv;
1931 17     ...
1932 18 }

```

Listing 6: Example of annotations added.

A.10 Developer Survey

A.10.1 Respondent Experience with C and RUST. The heatmap in Figure 15 shows the distribution of developers who have converted projects from C-to-RUST, categorized by their experience in each language. The data represented as x/y indicates that out of y developers with the given experience, only x have carried out any C-to-RUST conversion. Most respondents attempting this conversion have beginner (1-3 years) to moderate (3-5 years) experience in both languages. Notably, a considerable number of experienced C developers also have experience with RUST, suggesting that high proficiency in C does not deter developers from transitioning to RUST.

A.11 RQ2.2: Motivation for Conversion and Perceived Benefits

Here, we explore the motivation for attempting C-to-RUST conversion and the perceived benefits of the resulting RUST code.

Motivation. The Figure 18 displays an upset plot [44] illustrating the reasons reported by developers for attempting conversion. Developers can choose multiple motivations, and the plot shows the unique combinations along with the total number of developers who selected each. For example in Figure 18, 14 developers cited maintainability, while four selected maintainability, security, and interoperability.

Expectedly, maintainability (67%) and security (38%) are two major motivations – as RUST provides streamlined package management and memory safety. Interestingly, for many (43%) developers, the motivation for conversion is to learn RUST. Upon deeper investigation, we found that the majority of the reported developers have considerable experience in C programming. This provides evidence that *conversion exercises could be a good RUST language teaching modality, specifically for developers with experience in C*. Interoperability is an interesting motivation, and as we will discuss in § ??, this is to use existing C libraries in new RUST code.

Benefits. The majority (> 80%) of developers claim that RUST code produced after conversion will have higher security and maintainability. The Figure 10 shows the exact distribution. This is expected as maintainability and security were the two major motivations for conversion. Developers have mixed opinions on performance, with 66% claiming no performance benefit, while others think RUST code is faster. This indicates the need for a systematic performance study

Table 7: Reasons for unsafe functions in the output produced by tools.

Reason	C2RUST	CROWN	LAERTES	CRUSTS [▲]	CONCRAT	NOPCRAT	C2SAFERRUST
Access to Union Field	138 (0.85%)	140 (1.93%)	6 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	24 (0.30%)	0 (0.00%)
Deref of Raw Pointer	9,104 (56.23%)	3,968 (54.61%)	6,266 (55.42%)	0 (0.00%)	1,107 (52.94%)	3,993 (49.52%)	907 (39.97%)
Use of Extern Static	56 (0.35%)	29 (0.40%)	56 (0.50%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	27 (0.33%)	6 (0.26%)
Use of Mutable Static	134 (0.83%)	0 (0.00%)	119 (1.05%)	0 (0.00%)	8 (0.38%)	134 (1.66%)	4 (0.18%)
Call to Unsafe Function	5,724 (35.35%)	2,692 (37.05%)	4,034 (35.68%)	0 (0.00%)	950 (45.43%)	3,057 (37.91%)	769 (33.89%)
Borrow of Layout Constrained Field	224 (1.38%)	35 (0.48%)	137 (1.21%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	191 (2.37%)	7 (0.31%)
No Reason	811 (5.01%)	402 (5.53%)	688 (6.09%)	233 (100.00%)	26 (1.24%)	638 (7.91%)	576 (25.39%)
Total	16,191	7,266	11,306	233	2,091	8,064	2,269

[▲] Only a few programs converted by CRustS compile.

Figure 8: Non-array (Regular) Pointer Conversion (ExUB vs UxB vs RUB)

Table 8: Summary of Survey Questions.

Category	Description	Num.Qs
Developer's Experience	Examines participants' familiarity, experience with Rust and C language	9
C to Rust Expertise and Experience	Focuses on prior experience with porting C to Rust	5
Perceived Benefits of C to Rust	Investigates motivation, performance improvements, and benefits of converting C to Rust.	4
C to Rust Automated Tool Expertise & Experience	Examines usage, developer's perspective of conversion tools and challenges related to them	7
Tool Usage vs Manual Fixing	Explores the likelihood of usage of automated tools and manual fixing effort required for tool-generated Rust code	4
Manual Conversion Efforts	Assesses difficulties/challenges of manual conversion	4

of programs written in C and RUST. The recent study by Sharma *et al.* [66] also made the same observation for embedded codebases.

A.11.1 Survey Questions.

- Which of the following accurately describes your role in software development?
 - Developer
 - QA Engineer

- Project Manager
 - Other (Please specify)
- How many years of experience do you have with programming in C?
 - Less than a year
 - 1-3 Years
 - 3-5 Years
 - 5-10 Years

Figure 9: Key characteristics of converted C projects.

Figure 10: Benefits of converted Rust code vs. original C.

- More than 10 Years
- (3) Have you worked with Rust before?
 - Yes
 - No
- (4) How many lines of Rust code have you written (Approximately)?
 - Less than 100
 - 100-1K
 - 1K-5K
 - 5K-10K
 - More than 10K
- (5) How many years of experience do you have with programming in Rust?
 - Less than a year
 - 1-3 Years
 - 3-5 Years
 - 5-10 Years
 - More than 10 Years
- (6) How do you rate your experience with Rust?
 - Beginner
 - Intermediate
 - Advanced
 - Expert
- (7) How many applications have you developed using Rust?
 - 1-5

Figure 11: Challenges faced by developers in manual conversion based on RUST expertise.

Figure 12: Solutions explored to manual conversion challenges based on RUST expertise.

- 5-20
- 20-50
- More than 50
- (8) Have you ported C code to Rust before?
 - Yes
 - No
- (9) What motivated you to convert C to Rust? (Select all that apply)
 - Organization Requirement (e.g., company-wide policy)
 - To improve security of the code
 - To improve maintainability of the code
 - To improve performance
 - To learn Rust
 - To improve interoperability
 - Other (Please specify)
- (10) How would you rate the performance of the converted Rust code compared to the original C code?
 - Much Better
 - Better
 - About the Same
 - Worse
 - Much Worse
 - Don't know
- (11) How would you rate the safety and reliability of the converted Rust code compared to the original C code?
 - Much Better
 - Better
 - About the Same
 - Worse
 - Much Worse
 - Don't know

Figure 13: Summary of Issues and Fixes for Conversion Tools.

Figure 14: Manual effort for fixing the code.

- (12) How would you rate the maintainability of the converted Rust code compared to the original C code?
- Much Better
 - Better
 - About the Same
 - Worse
 - Much Worse
 - Don't know
- (13) What type of projects did you port from C to Rust? (Select all that apply)
- User mode applications
 - Low level utilities
 - System Software/OS components
 - Embedded Systems
 - Web Applications
 - Libraries
 - Other (Please specify)

Figure 15: Proportions of respondents who have ported C code to Rust, based on their experience levels in both programming languages.

Figure 16: Developer's rating for C to RUST porting resources.

- (14) Size of the C codebase you ported:
- Small (Less than 1,000 lines)
 - Medium (1,000 - 10,000 lines)
 - Large (More than 10,000 lines)
- (15) Did you use any tool while converting the codebase?
- Yes
 - No
- (16) Which tools have you worked with for conversion? (Select all that apply)
- C2rust
 - Bindgen
 - Laertes
 - CrustS
 - RustFix
 - Large Language Models (e.g. ChatGPT, Copilot, etc)
 - Other (Please specify)
- (17) How would you rate the usefulness of these tools?
- Very Useful
 - Useful
 - Neutral
 - Not Useful
- (18) Which one was best fit in your opinion?
- C2rust
 - Bindgen
 - Laertes
 - CrustS
 - RustFix
 - LLMs
 - Other (Please specify)

(a) Issues with automated C→RUST conversion techniques.

(b) Setup difficulty, robustness, and code quality.

Figure 17: Survey results on conversion tools. (a) Issues encountered. (b) Tool setup/robustness/quality.

Figure 18: Motivation for conversion from C to Rust

- (19) How easy/difficult was it to set up (i.e., install and use) the best fit conversion tool?
- Easy
 - Moderate
 - Difficult
 - Very difficult
- (20) How often did you face robustness issues (e.g., tool failing)?
- Always
 - Quite often
 - Often
 - Rarely
 - Very Rarely
 - Never

- (21) How satisfied were you with the quality of the produced Rust Code?
- Very satisfied
 - Somewhat satisfied
 - Neutral
 - Somewhat dissatisfied
 - Very dissatisfied
- (22) What improvements do you think current c to rust conversion tools need? (Select all that apply)
- Handling large codebases
 - Handling raw pointers
 - Handling type conversion
 - Produce less unsafe blocks
 - More robust (less tool errors)
 - Produce 1-1 line correspondence with C code
 - Produce more idiomatic Rust code
 - Other (Please specify)
- (23) How often did you have to do manual fixing of the tool-produced Rust code?
- Always
 - Quite often
 - Often
 - Rarely
 - Very Rarely
 - Never
- (24) What type of manual fixes did you have to do to the tool-produced Rust code? (Select all that apply)
- Stylistic (e.g., naming, formatting)
 - Types (e.g., pointers to vec/references)
 - Adding lifetime annotations
 - Adding imports / changes related to external functions
 - Handling inline assembly
 - Handling access to unions/struct fields
 - FFI related changes
 - Converting unsafe blocks to safe blocks
 - Others (Please specify)
- (25) How much effort (to the best of your knowledge) is required to do the additional manual fixing of the tool produced Rust code?
- Very low
 - Low
 - Medium
 - High
 - Very high
- (26) What highlevel procedure you follow for Tool-assisted C to Rust conversion?
- Tool + manual fixes
 - Manual fixes + Tool
 - Tool + manual fixes + Tool
 - Multiple interleavings of tool and manual fixes
- (27) Did you ever manually convert C to Rust?
- Yes
 - No
- (28) What were the biggest challenges you faced while manually porting C code to Rust? (Select all that apply)
- Understanding Rust syntax and semantics
 - Dealing with Rust's ownership model

2437	• Performance issues	2495
2438	• Compatibility with existing C libraries	2496
2439	• Debugging and testing	2497
2440	• Other (Please specify)	2498
2441	(29) How did you address these challenges? (Select all that apply)	2499
2442		2500
2443	• Online documentation and tutorials	2501
2444	• Community forums and support	2502
2445	• Trial (e.g., trying to compile) and fix	2503
2446	• Other (Please specify)	2504
2447	(30) How would you rate the documentation and resources available for porting C code to Rust?	2505
2448		2506
2449	• Very Helpful	2507
2450	• Somewhat helpful	2508
2451	• Missing technicalities	2509
2452	• Have fewer examples	2510
2453	• Other (Please specify)	2511
2454		2512
2455	Received 20 February 2007; revised 12 March 2009; accepted 5 June 2009	2513
2456		2514
2457		2515
2458		2516
2459		2517
2460		2518
2461		2519
2462		2520
2463		2521
2464		2522
2465		2523
2466		2524
2467		2525
2468		2526
2469		2527
2470		2528
2471		2529
2472		2530
2473		2531
2474		2532
2475		2533
2476		2534
2477		2535
2478		2536
2479		2537
2480		2538
2481		2539
2482		2540
2483		2541
2484		2542
2485		2543
2486		2544
2487		2545
2488		2546
2489		2547
2490		2548
2491		2549
2492		2550
2493		2551
2494		2552